

Navier-Stokes Equations in Cylindrical Coordinates: A First-Principles Derivation

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1 Introduction

The Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible Newtonian flow in cylindrical coordinates are fundamental to the analysis of pipe flows, rotating machinery, and a wide range of axisymmetric fluid systems. While the final forms of these equations are stated in most standard fluid mechanics textbooks [1, 3, 4], the complete step-by-step derivation from first principles — including the force balance on an infinitesimal cylindrical element, the construction of the viscous stress tensor in curvilinear coordinates, and the role of curvature forces — is rarely presented in full detail. This often leaves students and early-career researchers to piece together the derivation from disparate sources.

The purpose of this paper is therefore *pedagogical*: it provides a self-contained, first-principles derivation of the governing equations for incompressible flow in cylindrical coordinates, proceeding from the kinematic relations between Cartesian and cylindrical systems through the momentum and continuity equations, Newton's viscosity law adapted for curvilinear coordinates, non-dimensionalisation revealing the Reynolds number as the sole governing parameter, and finally the essential boundary conditions for pipe flow. No new physics is claimed; the contribution lies in consolidating the entire derivation chain into a single, accessible document with explicit intermediate steps and explanatory remarks at points where the cylindrical geometry introduces subtleties absent in Cartesian formulations.

2 Notation

Serial No.	Annotation	Description
1	x	Cartesian Horizontal Axis/Distance
2	y	Cartesian Vertical Axis/Distance
3	z	Axial Direction (Cartesian + Cylindrical)
4	r	Radial Direction
5	θ	Azimuthal Direction
6	δz	Discretized Axial Length
7	δr	Discretized Radial Length
8	$\delta\theta$	Discretized Angular Distance
9	\hat{i}	Unit vector along X axis
10	\hat{j}	Unit vector along Y axis
11	\hat{k}	Unit vector along Z axis in Cartesian Coordinate
12	\hat{e}_r	Unit Vector along Radial Direction from central axis
13	\hat{e}_θ	Unit Vector along Azimuthal Direction from XY Plane
14	\hat{e}_z	Unit Vector along Z axis in Cylindrical Coordinate
15	\vec{p}	Position Vector of a point or element in both coordinate systems
16	\vec{V}	Net Velocity of a point or element in both coordinate systems
17	u_z	Axial Velocity Magnitude
18	u_r	Radial Velocity Magnitude
19	u_θ	Azimuth Velocity Magnitude
20	P	Pressure
21	Re	Reynolds Number
22	t	time
23	δt	time change
24	ν	Kinematic Viscosity
25	μ	Dynamic Viscosity
26	ρ	Density
27	τ_{ij}	Shear Stress on i^{th} face in j^{th} direction
28	F	Force
29	KN	Knudsen Number

3 Derivation of the Governing Equations

To understand the physics behind the pipe flow problem, we must derive the governing equations that the fluid obeys while flowing through the domain of interest.

3.1 Assumptions for the derivation

1. The fluid is incompressible, i.e., ρ is constant with space and time throughout the flow field.
2. The fluid behaviour is not initially specified to be of any particular type, but towards the end of the derivation it will be assumed to be Newtonian. This means it obeys Newton's law of viscosity, i.e., $\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right)$
3. The control volume is stationary and non-accelerating. No gravitational force acts on the flow; the only external force is the pressure force.
4. The continuum hypothesis holds, i.e., $KN \ll 1$.
5. Pressure acts only normal to a plane or surface as a compressive force and is the only external force acting.

3.2 Pictorial Representation of Flow Domain

(a) Front View of the Cylindrical Flow Domain

(b) Mid-Longitudinal Cross-Sectional View of the Cylindrical Flow Domain

Each cell in the domain represents a discretized element or control volume. Within each volume, the fluid is assumed to share common properties such as pressure and velocities along the three cylindrical coordinate directions. Each cell is bounded by 6 surfaces, namely top, bottom, left, right, front, and back, as seen from the viewer's perspective. While pressure acts only in the normal direction to each face, each face also has 3 components of stress acting along the 3 coordinate directions: \hat{e}_r , \hat{e}_θ , and \hat{e}_z .

3.3 Kinematic relation between Cartesian and Cylindrical coordinate systems

(a) 3D Cartesian Coordinate Geometry for Locating a Point and Initializing a Vector

(b) Relation Between Cartesian and Polar Coordinates

Figure 2: Comparison of Cartesian Coordinates and Polar Coordinates

In this section, we focus on how the relations between a Cartesian x, y, z system can be used to derive the polar r, θ, z system. The fundamental difference between a Cartesian and a cylindrical/polar coordinate system stems from the fact that in the Cartesian system, the basis vectors have no variation in direction with time; they remain fixed throughout the calculation. Once defined with respect to the body, their orientation does not change. However, this is not the case with the polar coordinate system, as the two basis vectors \hat{e}_r and \hat{e}_θ rotate with time and continuously change direction. Therefore, we begin with the fixed Cartesian system as our absolute reference frame for the initial derivation. Consider a **point P** located in space where a Cartesian system is

well-defined, with its origin at **point O** and three mutually perpendicular planes (XY, YZ, and ZX) whose intersections define the three coordinate axes x , y , and z , with respective unit vectors \hat{i} , \hat{j} , and \hat{k} . Thus,

$$\vec{p} = x\hat{i} + y\hat{j} + z\hat{k}$$

As is well known, the z axis is the same in both Cartesian and polar coordinates, merely denoted by different basis vectors: \hat{k} in Cartesian and \hat{e}_z in cylindrical. Thus, we are primarily interested in the relationship between the XY and $R\theta$ directions. Consider a plane parallel to XY that also contains point P, and let \vec{r} be the vector from the z axis to P, parallel to the XY plane, with r being its magnitude. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{r} &= x\hat{i} + y\hat{j} \\ \Rightarrow \vec{r} &= r \cos \theta \hat{i} + r \sin \theta \hat{j} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\vec{r}}{r} &= \cos \theta \hat{i} + \sin \theta \hat{j} \\ \Rightarrow \hat{e}_r &= \cos \theta \hat{i} + \sin \theta \hat{j}\end{aligned}$$

This is the representation of the radial unit vector. Since the axial unit vector is identical to the Cartesian z axis, it can be written as $\hat{e}_z = \hat{k}$. To find the azimuthal unit vector, we use the properties of basis vectors. Let $\hat{e}_\theta = a\hat{i} + b\hat{j}$. The first property is that any two basis vectors in a coordinate system must be orthonormal, which implies their dot product is zero:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{e}_\theta \cdot \hat{e}_r &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow (a\hat{i} + b\hat{j}) \cdot (\cos \theta \hat{i} + \sin \theta \hat{j}) &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow a \cos \theta + b \sin \theta &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow a &= \frac{-b \sin \theta}{\cos \theta}\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

The second property is that the magnitude of a unit vector is always unity:

$$\begin{aligned}|a\hat{i} + b\hat{j}| &= 1 \\ a^2 + b^2 &= 1\end{aligned}$$

Substituting a from equation 1:

$$\begin{aligned}b^2 \left(\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{\cos^2 \theta} + 1 \right) &= 1 \\ \Rightarrow b^2 &= \cos^2 \theta \\ \Rightarrow b &= \pm \cos \theta\end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\Rightarrow a = \mp \sin \theta$$

The choice between \pm and \mp is ours to make; however, choosing $b = +\cos \theta$ (and hence $a = -\sin \theta$) makes the angular basis anticlockwise-positive, which follows the right-hand rule convention. Thus, the three basis vectors are:

$$\hat{e}_r = \cos \theta \hat{i} + \sin \theta \hat{j} \quad , \quad \hat{e}_\theta = -\sin \theta \hat{i} + \cos \theta \hat{j} \quad , \quad \hat{e}_z = \hat{k}$$

Therefore,

$$\vec{p} = x\hat{i} + y\hat{j} + z\hat{k} = r(\cos \theta \hat{i} + \sin \theta \hat{j}) + z\hat{k} = r\hat{e}_r + z\hat{e}_z$$

Differentiating the above equation with respect to time, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{V}_{\text{net}} &= \frac{d\vec{p}}{dt} = \frac{dr}{dt} \hat{e}_r + r \frac{d\hat{e}_r}{dt} + \frac{dz}{dt} \hat{e}_z + z \frac{d\hat{e}_z}{dt} \\ \Rightarrow \vec{V}_{\text{net}} &= u_r \hat{e}_r + r \frac{d(\cos \theta \hat{i} + \sin \theta \hat{j})}{dt} + u_z \hat{e}_z + z \frac{d\hat{e}_z}{dt} \\ \Rightarrow \vec{V}_{\text{net}} &= u_r \hat{e}_r + r \left(-\sin \theta \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{i} + \cos \theta \frac{d\hat{i}}{dt} + \cos \theta \frac{d\theta}{dt} \hat{j} + \sin \theta \frac{d\hat{j}}{dt} \right) + u_z \hat{e}_z + z \frac{d\hat{e}_z}{dt}\end{aligned}$$

Since \hat{i} , \hat{j} , and $\hat{k} = \hat{e}_z$ do not change with time, they are constants; hence $\frac{d\hat{i}}{dt} = \frac{d\hat{j}}{dt} = \frac{d\hat{k}}{dt} = \frac{d\hat{e}_z}{dt} = 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}\Rightarrow \vec{V}_{\text{net}} &= u_r \hat{e}_r + r \frac{d\theta}{dt} (-\sin \theta \hat{i} + \cos \theta \hat{j}) + u_z \hat{e}_z \\ \Rightarrow \vec{V}_{\text{net}} &= u_r \hat{e}_r + u_\theta \hat{e}_\theta + u_z \hat{e}_z\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

The following important relations emerge from the above derivation:

$$\frac{d\hat{e}_r}{dt} = \frac{d(\cos\theta \hat{i} + \sin\theta \hat{j})}{dt} = \frac{d\theta}{dt} (-\sin\theta \hat{i} + \cos\theta \hat{j}) = \omega \hat{e}_\theta = \frac{u_\theta}{r} \hat{e}_\theta$$

Similarly,

$$\frac{d\hat{e}_\theta}{dt} = \frac{d(-\sin\theta \hat{i} + \cos\theta \hat{j})}{dt} = -\frac{d\theta}{dt} (\cos\theta \hat{i} + \sin\theta \hat{j}) = -\omega \hat{e}_r = -\frac{u_\theta}{r} \hat{e}_r$$

Now, differentiating equation 2 with respect to time:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{a}_{\text{net}} &= \frac{d\vec{V}_{\text{net}}}{dt} = \frac{d(u_r \hat{e}_r + u_\theta \hat{e}_\theta + u_z \hat{e}_z)}{dt} \\ \Rightarrow \vec{a}_{\text{net}} &= \frac{du_r}{dt} \hat{e}_r + u_r \frac{d\hat{e}_r}{dt} + \frac{du_\theta}{dt} \hat{e}_\theta + u_\theta \frac{d\hat{e}_\theta}{dt} + \frac{du_z}{dt} \hat{e}_z + u_z \frac{d\hat{e}_z}{dt} \\ \Rightarrow \vec{a}_{\text{net}} &= \frac{du_r}{dt} \hat{e}_r + \frac{u_r u_\theta}{r} \hat{e}_\theta + \frac{du_\theta}{dt} \hat{e}_\theta - \frac{u_\theta^2}{r} \hat{e}_r + \frac{du_z}{dt} \hat{e}_z \\ \Rightarrow \frac{d\vec{V}_{\text{net}}}{dt} &= \vec{a}_{\text{net}} = \left(\frac{du_r}{dt} - \frac{u_\theta^2}{r} \right) \hat{e}_r + \left(\frac{u_r u_\theta}{r} + \frac{du_\theta}{dt} \right) \hat{e}_\theta + \frac{du_z}{dt} \hat{e}_z \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

This is the expression for acceleration in a cylindrical coordinate system, and it will be used in the force analysis to obtain the dimensional cylindrical Navier-Stokes equations.

4 Dynamic Analysis of the Cylindrical Flow Field

We now subdivide the system into discrete elements and analyse a single representative element. The figure below depicts its various faces, and the accompanying table lists the areas, velocities, pressures, and stresses acting on each face. Now we will apply the

Face	Area	Velocity	Pressure	Axial Stress	Radial Stress	Azimuthal Stress
Back	$r\delta r\delta\theta$	u_z	P	τ_{zz}	τ_{zr}	$\tau_{z\theta}$
Front	$r\delta r\delta\theta$	$u_z + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \delta z$	$P + \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \delta z$	$\tau_{zz} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \delta z$	$\tau_{zr} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zr}}{\partial z} \delta z$	$\tau_{z\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} \delta z$
Top	$(r + \delta r) \delta\theta \delta z$	$u_r + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \delta r$	$P + \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \delta r$	$\tau_{rz} + \frac{\partial \tau_{rz}}{\partial r} \delta r$	$\tau_{rr} + \frac{\partial \tau_{rr}}{\partial r} \delta r$	$\tau_{r\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} \delta r$
Bottom	$r\delta\theta\delta z$	u_r	P	τ_{rz}	τ_{rr}	$\tau_{r\theta}$
Right	$\delta z \delta r$	u_θ	P	$\tau_{\theta z}$	$\tau_{\theta r}$	$\tau_{\theta\theta}$
Left	$\delta z \delta r$	$u_\theta + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta$	$P + \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta$	$\tau_{\theta z} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta z}}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta$	$\tau_{\theta r} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta r}}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta$	$\tau_{\theta\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta$

Table 1: Flow parameters and stresses across different faces of the pipe.

Figure 3: Different Aspects of a cylindrical element with mass flow and force analysis

basic conservation laws of mass and momentum to derive the governing equations.

4.1 Continuity Equation

The continuum assumption allows us to use differential equations to formulate the governing equations. The mass conservation law states that **mass can neither be created nor destroyed under the classical continuum hypothesis**. Therefore, we deduce that:

$$\text{Mass entering the flow field} = \text{Mass leaving the flow field} + \text{Mass accumulated in the flow field}$$

$$\Rightarrow M_{\text{inlet}} = M_{\text{outlet}} + M_{\text{stored}}$$

Differentiating the above equation with respect to time, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \frac{dM_{\text{inlet}}}{dt} &= \frac{dM_{\text{outlet}}}{dt} + \frac{dM_{\text{stored}}}{dt} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{d(\rho V_{\text{inlet}})}{dt} &= \frac{d(\rho V_{\text{outlet}})}{dt} + \frac{d(\rho V_{\text{stored}})}{dt} \end{aligned}$$

Since the flow is incompressible, ρ cancels from both sides. Additionally, since the control volume does not change with time, $\frac{dV_{\text{stored}}}{dt} = 0$. Therefore,

$$\Rightarrow \frac{dV_{\text{inlet}}}{dt} = \frac{dV_{\text{outlet}}}{dt}$$

As can be seen from Figures 3a and 3b, mass enters through the bottom, right, and front surfaces, and exits through the top, left, and back surfaces. Therefore,

$$\frac{dV_{\text{front}}}{dt} + \frac{dV_{\text{bottom}}}{dt} + \frac{dV_{\text{right}}}{dt} = \frac{dV_{\text{back}}}{dt} + \frac{dV_{\text{top}}}{dt} + \frac{dV_{\text{left}}}{dt}$$

Since the cross-sectional areas of the surfaces are independent of time, only the flow length is affected. Upon differentiation, this converts to velocity:

$$u_{\text{front}}A_{\text{front}} + u_{\text{bottom}}A_{\text{bottom}} + u_{\text{right}}A_{\text{right}} = u_{\text{back}}A_{\text{back}} + u_{\text{top}}A_{\text{top}} + u_{\text{left}}A_{\text{left}}$$

$$\Rightarrow u_z \cdot r \delta r \delta \theta + u_r \cdot r \delta \theta \delta z + u_\theta \cdot \delta r \delta z = \left(u_z + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \delta z \right) \cdot r \delta r \delta \theta + \left(u_r + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \delta r \right) \cdot (r + \delta r) \delta \theta \delta z + \left(u_\theta + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \delta \theta \right) \cdot \delta r \delta z$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow u_z r \delta r \delta \theta + u_r \cdot r \delta \theta \delta z + u_\theta \cdot \delta r \delta z &= u_z r \delta r \delta \theta + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \delta z r \delta r \delta \theta + u_r r \delta \theta \delta z + u_r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \delta r r \delta \theta \delta z + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \delta r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z + \\ &u_\theta \delta r \delta z + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \delta \theta \delta r \delta z \end{aligned}$$

Canceling the common terms, we get:

$$0 = \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} r \delta z \delta r \delta \theta + u_r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \delta r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \delta \theta \delta r \delta z$$

Dividing by $\delta z \delta r \delta \theta$, we get:

$$r \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} + u_r + r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \delta r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} = 0$$

It is important to note that:

$$\frac{\partial(ru_r)}{\partial r} = u_r + r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \quad \& \quad \delta r \approx 0$$

So,

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\partial(ru_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + r \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = 0$$

Dividing by r , we obtain:

$$\boxed{\Rightarrow \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(ru_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = 0} \quad (4)$$

The above equation is known as the **Continuity Equation for Incompressible Flows for Cylindrical Coordinates**

4.2 The Three Momentum Equations

The momentum equations are derived by applying Newton's second law to an infinitesimal fluid element. A fluid in equilibrium — whether stationary or moving with a constant velocity — will maintain its original state as long as no external force acts upon it. This gives us the **Initial Condition** for the flow field. When an inlet pressure is subsequently applied, it pushes the fluid forward and causes changes in velocity, thereby altering the flow regime. In response to these external forces, the fluid develops internal stresses denoted by τ_{ij} on its various surfaces. The normal components of these stresses resist the compressive pressure force and are therefore tensile in nature, acting outward from the fluid body. The tangential (shear) components resist surface deformation and angular velocity changes. It is the interplay between these internal and external forces that governs the changes in fluid motion. So, the main points from the above discussion are:

- **PRESSURE** is the external hydrostatic force and the primary cause of changes in the fluid's motion. It acts as a compressive force on all faces.
- Stresses are internal resistive forces, collectively referred to as **VISCOUS FORCES**, that resist the fluid's motion. They are of two types: normal and shear. A single normal stress acts outward from each face, while shear stresses act tangentially in pairs to prevent rotational effects on the fluid element.

- An additional **CURVATURE** force arises because the angular path of the fluid is not straight, causing a hindrance to the inertia of a fluid particle that tends to move in a straight line. These forces affect only the radial and azimuthal directions, not the axial direction.
- It is important to note that when evaluating the pressure and viscous forces, only the translational components (i.e., along the radial and axial directions) are considered, and not the azimuthal component. This is because the azimuthal force analysis depends not only on the magnitude and direction of forces but also on the distance of the force from the central axis of rotation, which constitutes the **MOMENT OF FORCE**. This effect is fully accounted for in the **CURVATURE** force analysis.
- The net effect of all forces produces an acceleration of the fluid element along the flow field.

$$\vec{F}_{\text{net}} = \vec{F}_{\text{pressure}} + \vec{F}_{\text{viscous}} + \vec{F}_{\text{curvature}}$$

By Newton's second law of motion:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F}_{\text{net}} &= \frac{d(m\vec{V}_{\text{net}})}{dt} \\ \implies \frac{d(m\vec{V}_{\text{net}})}{dt} &= \vec{F}_{\text{pressure}} + \vec{F}_{\text{viscous}} + \vec{F}_{\text{curvature}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

From Figure (3c) and Table (1), we can deduce the pressure and viscous forces:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F}_{\text{pressure}} &= \left(P - \left(P + \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \delta z \right) \right) r \delta r \delta \theta \hat{e}_z + \left(Pr \delta r \delta z - \left(P + \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \delta r \right) (r + \delta r) \delta z \delta \theta \right) \hat{e}_r \\ \implies \vec{F}_{\text{pressure}} &= -\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_z - \left(P \delta r \delta z \delta \theta + \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} r \delta r \delta z \delta \theta + \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \delta r^2 \delta z \delta \theta \right) \hat{e}_r \\ \implies \vec{F}_{\text{pressure}} &= -\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_z - \left(\frac{P}{r} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{r} \right) r \delta r \delta z \delta \theta \hat{e}_r \end{aligned}$$

Along the radial direction, since $\delta r \approx 0$, the terms $\frac{P}{r} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial r}$ dominate over $\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{r}$. Therefore,

$$\implies \vec{F}_{\text{pressure}} = -\left(\frac{P}{r} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \right) r \delta r \delta z \delta \theta \hat{e}_r - \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_z \quad (6)$$

Remark: The P/r term appearing in the radial pressure force above is *not* a physical pressure gradient; it arises from the geometric difference in area between the inner face ($r \delta \theta \delta z$) and the outer face ($(r + \delta r) \delta \theta \delta z$) of the cylindrical element. An equal and opposite $+P/r$ term will appear in the curvature force (equation 8), and these cancel in the final combined momentum equation (9). This is expected — the net force must depend only on pressure *gradients*, not on absolute pressure level.

$$\begin{aligned} \implies \vec{F}_{\text{viscous}} &= \left(\left(\tau_{rr} + \frac{\partial \tau_{rr}}{\partial r} \delta r \right) (r + \delta r) \delta \theta \delta z + \left(\tau_{\theta r} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta r}}{\partial \theta} \delta \theta \right) \delta z \delta r + \left(\tau_{zr} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zr}}{\partial z} \delta z \right) r \delta \theta \delta r - \tau_{rr} r \delta \theta \delta z - \tau_{zr} r \delta \theta \delta r \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \tau_{\theta r} \delta r \delta z \right) \hat{e}_r + \left(\left(\tau_{zz} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \delta z \right) r \delta r \delta \theta + \left(\tau_{rz} + \frac{\partial \tau_{rz}}{\partial r} \delta r \right) (r + \delta r) \delta \theta \delta z + \left(\tau_{\theta z} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta z}}{\partial \theta} \delta \theta \right) \delta z \delta r - \tau_{zz} r \delta \theta \delta r - \tau_{\theta z} \delta z \delta r \right) \hat{e}_z \\ \implies \vec{F}_{\text{viscous}} &= \left(\tau_{rr} \delta r \delta \theta \delta z + r \frac{\partial \tau_{rr}}{\partial r} \delta r \delta \theta \delta z + \frac{\partial \tau_{rr}}{\partial r} \delta r^2 \delta \theta \delta z + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta r}}{\partial \theta} \delta \theta \delta z \delta r + \frac{\partial \tau_{zr}}{\partial z} r \delta \theta \delta r \delta z \right) \hat{e}_r + \\ &\quad \left(r \frac{\partial \tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \delta z \delta r \delta \theta + \tau_{rz} \delta r \delta \theta \delta z + r \frac{\partial \tau_{rz}}{\partial r} \delta r \delta \theta \delta z + \frac{\partial \tau_{rz}}{\partial r} \delta r^2 \delta \theta \delta z + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta z}}{\partial \theta} \delta \theta \delta z \delta r \right) \hat{e}_z \end{aligned}$$

Since $\delta r \rightarrow 0$, we have $\delta r^2 \approx 0$. Taking the common terms outside the brackets, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \implies \vec{F}_{\text{viscous}} &= \left(\left(\tau_{rr} + r \frac{\partial \tau_{rr}}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta r}}{\partial \theta} + r \frac{\partial \tau_{zr}}{\partial z} \right) \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_r + \left(\left(\tau_{rz} + r \frac{\partial \tau_{rz}}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta z}}{\partial \theta} + r \frac{\partial \tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \right) \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_z \\ \implies \vec{F}_{\text{viscous}} &= \left(\frac{\partial (r \tau_{rr})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta r}}{\partial \theta} + r \frac{\partial \tau_{zr}}{\partial z} \right) \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_r + \left(\frac{\partial (r \tau_{rz})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta z}}{\partial \theta} + r \frac{\partial \tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \right) \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_z \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

To determine the curvature effects, we examine the radial and azimuthal stress components and identify the additional forces. In the radial direction, the turning effect causes the normal azimuthal stress to have a radial component that acts like a centripetal force (directed towards the centre, causing rotary motion). In the azimuthal direction, the moment of forces must also be balanced and will be converted into an equivalent azimuthal force. **Note on the azimuthal component:** In the azimuthal direction, the force balance is performed via a *moment balance* about the central axis, then dividing by the moment arm $(r + \delta r/2)$ (the mid-radius of the element) to convert the torque back into an equivalent azimuthal force per unit volume. This is necessary because azimuthal forces at different radial positions exert different torques, and a direct force summation would not correctly account for the lever-arm effect in curvilinear coordinates.

Figure 4: Illustration of the Curvilinear Forces on the element

$$\vec{F}_{\text{curvature}} = \left(-\tau_{\theta\theta} \sin\left(\frac{\delta\theta}{2}\right) \delta r \delta z - \left(\tau_{\theta\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \right) \sin\left(\frac{\delta\theta}{2}\right) \delta r \delta z + P \sin\left(\frac{\delta\theta}{2}\right) \delta r \delta z + \left(P + \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \right) \sin\left(\frac{\delta\theta}{2}\right) \delta r \delta z \right) \hat{e}_r$$

$$+ \left(\frac{\left(\left(\tau_{r\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} \delta r \right) (r + \delta r)^2 \delta\theta \delta z - \tau_{r\theta} r^2 \delta\theta \delta z + \left(\tau_{z\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} \delta z \right) r \delta\theta \delta r \left(r + \frac{\delta r}{2} \right) - \tau_{z\theta} r \delta\theta \delta r \left(r + \frac{\delta r}{2} \right) + \left(\tau_{\theta\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \right) \delta z \delta r \left(r + \frac{\delta r}{2} \right) - \tau_{\theta\theta} \delta z \delta r \left(r + \frac{\delta r}{2} \right) - \left(P + \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \right) \delta z \delta r \left(r + \frac{\delta r}{2} \right) + P \delta z \delta r \left(r + \frac{\delta r}{2} \right) \right)}{r + \frac{\delta r}{2}} \right) \hat{e}_\theta$$

$$\because \delta\theta \rightarrow 0 \implies \sin\left(\frac{\delta\theta}{2}\right) = \frac{\delta\theta}{2} \quad \& \quad \frac{\delta r}{2} \ll r \text{ So we get that;}$$

$$\implies \vec{F}_{\text{curvature}} = \left(-\tau_{\theta\theta} \frac{\delta\theta}{2} - \tau_{\theta\theta} \frac{\delta\theta}{2} - \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \frac{\delta\theta}{2} + P \frac{\delta\theta}{2} + P \frac{\delta\theta}{2} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \frac{\delta\theta}{2} \right) \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_r +$$

$$\left(\frac{\left(\left(\tau_{r\theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} \delta r \right) (r^2 + 2r\delta r + \delta r^2) \delta\theta \delta z - \tau_{r\theta} r^2 \delta\theta \delta z + \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} \delta z r \delta\theta \delta r \left(r + \frac{\delta r}{2} \right) + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \delta z \delta r \left(r + \frac{\delta r}{2} \right) - \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \delta z \delta r \left(r + \frac{\delta r}{2} \right) \right)}{r + \frac{\delta r}{2}} \right) \hat{e}_\theta$$

$$\implies \vec{F}_{\text{curvature}} = \left(-\tau_{\theta\theta} \delta\theta + P \delta\theta - \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta\theta^2}{2} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta\theta^2}{2} \right) \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_r +$$

$$\left(\frac{\left(\tau_{r\theta} (2r + \delta r) \delta r \delta\theta \delta z + r^2 \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} \delta r \delta\theta \delta z + 2r \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} \delta r^2 \delta\theta \delta z + \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} \delta r^3 \delta\theta \delta z \right)}{r + \frac{\delta r}{2}} + \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} \delta z r \delta\theta \delta r + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \delta z \delta r - \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \delta\theta \delta z \delta r \right) \hat{e}_\theta$$

Neglecting higher powers of $\delta\theta$, δr , and δz , and extracting the common terms, we get:

$$\implies \vec{F}_{\text{curvature}} = (-\tau_{\theta\theta} + P) \delta\theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_r + \left(2\tau_{r\theta} + \frac{(r + \delta r)^2}{r + \frac{\delta r}{2}} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} + r \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \right) \delta\theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_\theta$$

Since $\delta r \ll r$, we can neglect δr when added to r . After simplification, we get:

$$\implies \vec{F}_{\text{curvature}} = (-\tau_{\theta\theta} + P) \delta\theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_r + \left(\frac{1}{r} \left(2r\tau_{r\theta} + r^2 \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} \right) + r \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \right) \delta\theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_\theta$$

Combining derivative terms where possible and factoring out r (as done for the other forces):

$$\implies \vec{F}_{\text{curvature}} = \left(-\frac{\tau_{\theta\theta}}{r} + \frac{P}{r} \right) r \delta\theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_r + \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial (r^2 \tau_{r\theta})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} \right) r \delta\theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_\theta \quad (8)$$

Substituting equations (6), (7), and (8) into (5):

$$\vec{F}_{\text{net}} = \vec{F}_{\text{pressure}} + \vec{F}_{\text{viscous}} + \vec{F}_{\text{curvature}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \frac{d(m\vec{V}_{\text{net}})}{dt} &= - \left(\frac{P}{r} + \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \right) r \delta r \delta z \delta \theta \hat{e}_r - \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_z + \left(\frac{\partial(r\tau_{rr})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta r}}{\partial\theta} + r \frac{\partial\tau_{zr}}{\partial z} \right) \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_r + \\ &\left(\frac{\partial(r\tau_{rz})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta z}}{\partial\theta} + r \frac{\partial\tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \right) \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_z + \left(-\frac{\tau_{\theta\theta}}{r} + \frac{P}{r} \right) r \delta \theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_r + \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial(r^2\tau_{r\theta})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial\tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial\theta} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial\theta} \right) r \delta \theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_\theta \end{aligned}$$

Expanding the left-hand side and grouping terms by their basis vectors, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \vec{V}_{\text{net}} \frac{dm}{dt} + m \frac{d\vec{V}_{\text{net}}}{dt} &= \left(-\frac{P}{r} - \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\tau_{rr})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta r}}{\partial\theta} + \frac{\partial\tau_{zr}}{\partial z} - \frac{\tau_{\theta\theta}}{r} + \frac{P}{r} \right) r \delta r \delta z \delta \theta \hat{e}_r + \\ &\left(-\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\tau_{rz})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta z}}{\partial\theta} + \frac{\partial\tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \right) r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_z + \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial(r^2\tau_{r\theta})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial\tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial\theta} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial\theta} \right) r \delta \theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_\theta \end{aligned}$$

Since the mass within the CV is constant, $\frac{dm}{dt} = 0$. The mass of fluid within the CV is given by $m = \rho r \delta \theta \delta r \delta z$. Substituting this expression for m and using the acceleration from equation (3), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \rho r \delta \theta \delta r \delta z \left(\left(\frac{du_r}{dt} - \frac{u_\theta^2}{r} \right) \hat{e}_r + \left(\frac{u_r u_\theta}{r} + \frac{du_\theta}{dt} \right) \hat{e}_\theta + \frac{du_z}{dt} \hat{e}_z \right) &= \left(-\frac{P}{r} - \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\tau_{rr})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta r}}{\partial\theta} + \frac{\partial\tau_{zr}}{\partial z} - \frac{\tau_{\theta\theta}}{r} + \frac{P}{r} \right) r \delta r \delta z \delta \theta \hat{e}_r \\ &+ \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial(r^2\tau_{r\theta})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial\tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial\theta} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial\theta} \right) r \delta \theta \delta r \delta z \hat{e}_\theta + \left(-\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\tau_{rz})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta z}}{\partial\theta} + \frac{\partial\tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \right) r \delta r \delta \theta \delta z \hat{e}_z \end{aligned}$$

Canceling $r \delta \theta \delta r \delta z$ from both sides:

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \rho \left(\left(\frac{du_r}{dt} - \frac{u_\theta^2}{r} \right) \hat{e}_r + \left(\frac{u_r u_\theta}{r} + \frac{du_\theta}{dt} \right) \hat{e}_\theta + \frac{du_z}{dt} \hat{e}_z \right) &= \left(-\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\tau_{rr})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta r}}{\partial\theta} + \frac{\partial\tau_{zr}}{\partial z} - \frac{\tau_{\theta\theta}}{r} \right) \hat{e}_r \\ &+ \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial(r^2\tau_{r\theta})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial\tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial\theta} - \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial\theta} \right) \hat{e}_\theta + \left(-\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\tau_{rz})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta z}}{\partial\theta} + \frac{\partial\tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \right) \hat{e}_z \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

This is the exact governing equation for an incompressible cylindrical pipe flow. We now focus on expressing the total derivatives of velocities with respect to time. Using the multivariable chain rule, the total derivative of a function equals the sum of its partial derivatives with respect to all dependent parameters:

$$\frac{du}{dt} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \frac{dx}{dt} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \frac{dy}{dt} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \frac{dz}{dt}$$

Applying this to all three velocity components in the cylindrical coordinate system:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{du_r}{dt} &= \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \frac{dr}{dt} + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} \frac{d\theta}{dt} + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} \frac{dz}{dt} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{du_r}{dt} &= \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Similarly, for the other two components:

$$\Rightarrow \frac{du_\theta}{dt} = \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \quad (11)$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{du_z}{dt} = \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \quad (12)$$

Separating equation (9) by basis vector components and substituting equations (10), (11), and (12), we obtain:

1. Radial Momentum Equation

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} - \frac{u_\theta^2}{r} \right) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\tau_{rr})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta r}}{\partial\theta} + \frac{\partial\tau_{zr}}{\partial z} - \frac{\tau_{\theta\theta}}{r} \quad (13)$$

2. Azimuthal Momentum Equation

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} + \frac{u_r u_\theta}{r} \right) = -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial(r^2\tau_{r\theta})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial\tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial\theta} \quad (14)$$

3. Axial Momentum Equation

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\tau_{rz})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta z}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial\tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \quad (15)$$

These are the governing equations for any incompressible flow in a cylindrical geometry such as pipe flows. They can be verified from “**Boundary-Layer Theory**” by **Schlichting and Gersten** [1], Chapter 3.13, Page 79, where these are listed as the main governing equations for cylindrical coordinate systems (though the detailed derivation is not presented there). We now shift our focus to Newtonian fluid flows. According to Newton’s Law of Viscosity, the shear stress on a fluid is proportional to the shear strain rate of the surface on which the stress acts:

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right)$$

This form is generally used for Cartesian coordinates, where all basis vectors are independent of one another. For a cylindrical system, it must be modified as explained below using basic principles.

4.3 Newton’s Law of Viscosity for the Cylindrical Basis System

Figure (5) illustrates the various velocity components acting on a differential fluid element with dimensions δr , $r\delta\theta$, and δz . The velocities are assumed to act about the central point of the element in their respective basis vector directions \hat{e}_r , \hat{e}_θ , and \hat{e}_z . Using Taylor series expansion to evaluate these velocities on all surfaces and neglecting higher-order terms, we obtain:

Element Face	Radial Velocity	Azimuthal Velocity	Axial Velocity
Top	$u_r + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2}$	$u_\theta + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2}$	$u_z + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2}$
Bottom	$u_r - \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2}$	$u_\theta - \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2}$	$u_z - \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2}$
Left	$u_r + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2}$	$u_\theta + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2}$	$u_z + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2}$
Right	$u_r - \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2}$	$u_\theta - \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2}$	$u_z - \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2}$
Front	$u_r + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2}$	$u_\theta + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2}$	$u_z + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2}$
Back	$u_r - \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2}$	$u_\theta - \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2}$	$u_z - \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2}$

Table 2: Table specifying the velocity components on various faces

Figure 5: Elemental figure to support the derivation

Using this table, we now derive expressions for all stress components:

$$\tau_{rr} = 2\mu \times \text{Rate of change of Radial strain along Radial Direction}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \tau_{rr} &= 2\mu \left(\frac{(u_r + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2}) - (u_r - \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2})}{\delta r} \right) \\ &\Rightarrow \tau_{rr} = 2\mu \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \end{aligned}$$

$$\tau_{\theta\theta} = 2\mu \times \text{Rate of change of Azimuthal Strain along Azimuthal Direction}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \tau_{\theta\theta} &= 2\mu \left(\frac{\frac{\partial(r\delta\theta)}{\partial t}}{r\delta\theta} \right) = 2\mu \left(\frac{r \frac{\partial(\delta\theta)}{\partial t} + \delta\theta \frac{\partial r}{\partial t}}{r\delta\theta} \right) \\ \Rightarrow \tau_{\theta\theta} &= 2\mu \left(\frac{(u_\theta + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2}) - (u_\theta - \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2})}{r\delta\theta} + \frac{u_r}{r} \right) \\ &\Rightarrow \tau_{\theta\theta} = 2\mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{u_r}{r} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\tau_{zz} = 2\mu \times \text{Rate of change of Axial strain along Axial Direction}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \tau_{zz} &= 2\mu \left(\frac{(u_z + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2}) - (u_z - \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2})}{\delta z} \right) \\ &\Rightarrow \tau_{zz} = 2\mu \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \end{aligned}$$

It is worth noting that since there is no net angular rotation of the control volume, all conjugate (symmetrical) stresses must be equal. Proceeding with the remaining six symmetrical stresses:

$\tau_{r\theta} = \tau_{\theta r} = \mu \times$ Rate of change of (Radial strain along Azimuthal Direction + Azimuthal strain along Radial Direction)

$$\implies \tau_{r\theta} = \mu \left(\frac{(u_r + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2}) - (u_r - \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2})}{r \delta \theta} + \left(\frac{(u_\theta + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2})}{r + \delta r} - \frac{(u_\theta - \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2})}{r} \right) \frac{r + \frac{\delta r}{2}}{\delta r} \right)$$

Note: The factor $(r + \frac{\delta r}{2})/\delta r$ in the second term normalizes the angular velocity difference by the physical radial distance δr at the mid-radius of the element, correctly converting the difference in azimuthal velocities (each divided by their respective radii to give angular velocities) into a strain rate.

$$\implies \tau_{r\theta} = \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \left(\frac{r u_\theta + r \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} \delta r - u_\theta (r + \delta r)}{r^2} \right) \frac{r}{\delta r} \right)$$

$$\implies \tau_{r\theta} = \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{u_\theta}{r} \right)$$

$\tau_{z\theta} = \tau_{\theta z} = \mu \times$ Rate of change of (Axial strain along Azimuthal Direction + Azimuthal strain along Axial Direction)

$$\implies \tau_{z\theta} = \mu \left(\frac{(u_z + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2}) - (u_z - \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} \frac{\delta \theta}{2})}{r \delta \theta} + \frac{(u_\theta + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2}) - (u_\theta - \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2})}{\delta z} \right)$$

$$\implies \tau_{z\theta} = \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \right)$$

$\tau_{zr} = \tau_{rz} = \mu \times$ Rate of change of (Axial strain along Radial Direction + Radial strain along Axial Direction)

$$\implies \tau_{zr} = \mu \left(\frac{(u_z + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2}) - (u_z - \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \frac{\delta r}{2})}{\delta r} + \frac{(u_r + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2}) - (u_r - \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} \frac{\delta z}{2})}{\delta z} \right)$$

$$\implies \tau_{zr} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} \right)$$

We now have all nine stress components expressed in terms of velocities:

$$\tau_{rr} = 2\mu \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \qquad \tau_{\theta\theta} = 2\mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{u_r}{r} \right) \qquad \tau_{zz} = 2\mu \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z}$$

$$\tau_{r\theta} = \tau_{\theta r} = \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{u_\theta}{r} \right) \qquad \tau_{zr} = \tau_{rz} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} \right) \qquad \tau_{\theta z} = \tau_{z\theta} = \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \right) \quad (16)$$

These relations (16) are the Newtonian constitutive relations for cylindrical coordinates. We can now proceed to derive the Navier-Stokes equations for Newtonian fluids in cylindrical coordinates.

4.4 Derivation of Dimensional N-S Equations for a Newtonian Fluid in Cylindrical Domain

Since we have already split the main equation into three separate momentum equations, the primary task is to simplify the right-hand side (RHS) of each. Solving each equation separately, we obtain:

- **RHS of Radial Momentum Equation (13):**

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(r\tau_{rr})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial\tau_{\theta r}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial\tau_{zr}}{\partial z} - \frac{\tau_{\theta\theta}}{r} \\ \implies & -\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \left(2\mu \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{u_\theta}{r} \right) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\mu \left(\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \right) \right) - \frac{2\mu}{r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{u_r}{r} \right) \\ \implies & -\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \left(\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \right) \right) + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta \partial r} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z \partial r} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} - \frac{2u_r}{r^2} \right) \\ \implies & -\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \left(\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} \right) \right) - \frac{u_r}{r^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(ru_r)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \right) \\ \implies & -\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(ru_r)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(ru_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Applying the continuity equation (4), this simplifies to:

$$\implies -\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(ru_r)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \right) \quad (17)$$

• **RHS of Azimuthal Momentum Equation (14):**

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial (r^2 \tau_{r\theta})}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta\theta}}{\partial \theta} \\
\Rightarrow & -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{u_\theta}{r} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} 2\mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{u_r}{r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \right) \\
\Rightarrow & -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} + \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta \partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} - \frac{u_\theta}{r^2} + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial z^2} \right) \\
\Rightarrow & -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} + \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_r}{r} \right) + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{u_\theta}{r} \right) + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial z^2} \right) \\
\Rightarrow & -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r u_\theta)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r u_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial z^2} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Applying the continuity equation (4), this simplifies to:

$$\Rightarrow -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r u_\theta)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (18)$$

• **RHS of Axial Momentum Equation (15):**

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r \tau_{rz})}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{\theta z}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \\
\Rightarrow & -\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} \right) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(2\mu \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) \\
\Rightarrow & -\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \right) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r u_r)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z^2} \right) \\
\Rightarrow & -\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \right) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r u_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z^2} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Applying the continuity equation (4), this simplifies to:

$$\Rightarrow -\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \mu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (19)$$

Substituting equations (17), (18), and (19) into equations (13), (14), and (15):

1. Radial Momentum Equation:

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} - \frac{u_\theta^2}{r} \right) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r u_r)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \right)$$

Dividing both sides by ρ :

$$\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} - \frac{u_\theta^2}{r} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r u_r)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \right) \quad (20)$$

Similarly, for the other two equations:

2. Azimuthal Momentum Equation:

$$\frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} + \frac{u_r u_\theta}{r} = -\frac{1}{r \rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r u_\theta)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (21)$$

3. Axial Momentum Equation:

$$\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \nu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z^2} \right) \quad (22)$$

4. Continuity Equation:

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial (r u_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (23)$$

These four equations — the continuity, radial momentum, azimuthal momentum, and axial momentum equations — are the cylindrical Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible Newtonian flow, and they provide the mathematical basis for solving pipe flow problems.

5 Non-Dimensionalisation of the Cylindrical N-S Equations

The above four equations — (20), (21), (22), and (23) — are in dimensional form, meaning they carry physical units such as metres/second for velocity, metres for length, kilograms for mass, etc. When studying the relative magnitudes of different terms in the equations, dimensional quantities are less convenient. Scientists therefore non-dimensionalise these expressions using known reference parameters such as inlet velocity, domain length scale, and fluid density. Other quantities such as the pressure scale and time scale can be derived from combinations of these references. The following table summarises the notation:

Parameter	Dimensional Variable	Non-Dimensional Variable
Axial Length	z	z^*
Radial Length	r	r^*
Azimuthal Angle	θ	θ
Axial Velocity	u_z	u_z^*
Azimuthal Velocity	u_θ	u_θ^*
Radial Velocity	u_r	u_r^*
Time	t	t^*
Density	ρ	ρ
Pressure	P	P^*

Table 3: Table showing the conversions of various parameters in the governing equations from dimensional to non-dimensional forms

The choice of reference scales and their justifications are discussed below:

- **Length Scale (L_{ref}):** We choose the pipe diameter D as our length scale, since it is typically the smallest characteristic length in a cylindrical flow problem.

$$L_{\text{ref}} = D$$

- **Velocity Scale (U_{ref}):** Since the inlet velocity is generally known, we select it as our reference. Among the three inlet velocity components (axial, radial, and azimuthal), the axial velocity is the most significant because it governs both the mass flow rate and the kinetic energy of the flow. We therefore choose $U_{z_{\text{avg}}}$ as the velocity reference.

$$u_{\text{ref}} = U_{z_{\text{avg}}}$$

- **Time Reference (t_{ref}):**

$$\because \text{Flow transit time} = \frac{\text{Length Traversed}}{\text{Average Velocity}}$$

So the time reference becomes as follows:

$$t_{\text{ref}} = \frac{l_{\text{ref}}}{U_{\text{ref}}}$$

- **Density Reference:** Since the fluid has a constant density throughout the flow (single-phase, no phase change), the density reference is simply the inlet density:

$$\rho_{\text{ref}} = \rho_{\text{inlet}}$$

- **Pressure/Stress Reference:** The reference pressure is taken as the dynamic pressure at the inlet:

$$p_{\text{ref}} = \frac{\text{Force input}}{\text{Area of Cross Section}}$$

$$\implies P_{\text{ref}} = \frac{\rho_{\text{ref}} U_{\text{ref}}^2 \frac{\pi D^2}{4}}{\frac{\pi D^2}{4}}$$

$$\implies P_{\text{ref}} = \rho_{\text{ref}} U_{\text{ref}}^2$$

The relations between dimensional and non-dimensional variables are as follows:

- Non-Dimensional Length: $L = L^* \times L_{\text{ref}}$

$$r = r^* \times D, \quad z = z^* \times D$$

- Non-Dimensional Velocity: $U = U^* \times U_{\text{ref}}$

$$u_r = u_r^* \times U_{z_{\text{avg}}}, \quad u_\theta = u_\theta^* \times U_{z_{\text{avg}}}, \quad u_z = u_z^* \times U_{z_{\text{avg}}}$$

- Non-Dimensional Time: $t = t^* \times t_{\text{ref}}$

$$t = t^* \times \frac{D}{U_{z\text{avg}}}$$

- Non-Dimensional Pressure: $P = P^* \times P_{\text{ref}}$

$$P = P^* \times \left(\rho_{\text{ref}} U_{z\text{avg}}^2 \right)$$

- Non-Dimensional Density: $\rho = \rho_{\text{inlet}}$ (since density is constant throughout the flow field).
- Non-Dimensional Angle: Since $\theta = \frac{\text{Arc Length}}{\text{Radius}}$ by definition, it is already non-dimensional.

We now proceed with the non-dimensionalisation of the governing equations:

1. Continuity Equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(ru_r)}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} &= 0 \\ \implies \frac{1}{r^* D} \frac{\partial(r^* D u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}})}{\partial r^* D} + \frac{1}{r^* D} \frac{\partial u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial z^* D} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying by $\frac{D}{U_{z\text{avg}}}$ since these are constants:

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial(r^* u_r^*)}{\partial r^*} + \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial z^*} = 0} \quad (24)$$

2. Radial Momentum Equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} - \frac{u_\theta^2}{r} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(ru_r)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} - \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} \right) \\ \implies \frac{\partial u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial t^* \left(\frac{D}{U_{z\text{avg}}} \right)} + u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}} \frac{\partial u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial r^* D} + \frac{u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{r^* D} \frac{\partial u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}} \frac{\partial u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial z^* D} - \frac{(u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}})^2}{r^* D} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial (P^* \rho U_{z\text{avg}}^2)}{\partial r^* D} + \\ \nu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r^* D} \left(\frac{1}{r^* D} \frac{\partial(r^* D u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}})}{\partial r^* D} \right) + \frac{\partial^2 u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{(r^* D)^2 \partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial (z^* D)^2} - \frac{2}{(r^* D)^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial \theta} \right) & \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying by $\frac{D}{U_{z\text{avg}}^2}$ since these are constants:

$$\implies \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial t^*} + u_r^* \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{u_\theta^*}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial z^*} - \frac{(u_\theta^*)^2}{r^*} = -\frac{\partial P^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{\nu}{DU_{z\text{avg}}} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial(r^* u_r^*)}{\partial r^*} \right) + \frac{\partial^2 u_r^*}{(r^*)^2 \partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} - \frac{2}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} \right)$$

As is well known, $\frac{DU_{z\text{avg}}}{\nu}$ is the most important non-dimensional parameter in fluid mechanics and is called the **Reynolds Number (Re)**. It represents the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces in the fluid, and flows with different Reynolds numbers exhibit fundamentally different characteristics. The equation thus becomes:

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial t^*} + u_r^* \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{u_\theta^*}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial z^*} - \frac{(u_\theta^*)^2}{r^*} = -\frac{\partial P^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial(r^* u_r^*)}{\partial r^*} \right) + \frac{\partial^2 u_r^*}{(r^*)^2 \partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} - \frac{2}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} \right)} \quad (25)$$

3. Azimuthal Momentum Equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} + \frac{u_r u_\theta}{r} &= -\frac{1}{r\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \theta} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial(ru_\theta)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{r^2} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial z^2} \right) \\ \implies \frac{\partial u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial t^* \frac{D}{U_{z\text{avg}}}} + u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}} \frac{\partial u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial r^* D} + \frac{u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{r^* D} \frac{\partial u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}} \frac{\partial u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial z^* D} + \frac{u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}} u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{r^* D} &= -\frac{1}{r^* D \rho} \frac{\partial P^* \rho U_{z\text{avg}}^2}{\partial \theta} + \\ \nu \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r^* D} \left(\frac{1}{r^* D} \frac{\partial(r^* D u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}})}{\partial r^* D} \right) + \frac{1}{(r^* D)^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{(r^* D)^2} \frac{\partial u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial (z^* D)^2} \right) & \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying by $\frac{D}{U_{z\text{avg}}^2}$ since these are constants:

$$\implies \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial t^*} + u_r^* \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{u_\theta^*}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial z^*} + \frac{u_r^* u_\theta^*}{r^*} = -\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial P^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\nu}{DU_{z\text{avg}}} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial(r^* u_\theta^*)}{\partial r^*} \right) + \frac{1}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} \right)$$

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial t^*} + u_r^* \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{u_\theta^*}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial z^*} + \frac{u_r^* u_\theta^*}{r^*} = -\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial P^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial(r^* u_\theta^*)}{\partial r^*} \right) + \frac{1}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} \right)} \quad (26)$$

4. Axial Momentum Equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} + u_z \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \nu \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z^2} \right) \\ \implies \frac{\partial u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial t^* \frac{D}{U_{z\text{avg}}}} + u_r^* U_{z\text{avg}} \frac{\partial u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial r^* D} + \frac{u_\theta^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{r^* D} \frac{\partial u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}} \frac{\partial u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial z^* D} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P^* \rho U_{z\text{avg}}^2}{\partial z} + \\ \nu \left(\frac{1}{r^* D} \frac{\partial}{\partial r^* D} \left(r^* D \left(\frac{\partial u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial r^* D} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{(r^* D)^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z^* U_{z\text{avg}}}{\partial (z^* D)^2} \right) & \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying by $\frac{D}{U_{z\text{avg}}^2}$ since these are constants:

$$\implies \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial t^*} + u_r^* \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{u_\theta^*}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial z^*} = -\frac{\partial P^*}{\partial z^*} + \frac{\nu}{DU_{z\text{avg}}} \left(\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(r^* \left(\frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial r^*} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_z^*}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} \right)$$

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial t^*} + u_r^* \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{u_\theta^*}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial z^*} = -\frac{\partial P^*}{\partial z^*} + \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(r^* \left(\frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial r^*} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_z^*}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} \right)} \quad (27)$$

Collecting the above four equations, we obtain the complete set of non-dimensional governing equations:

1. Non-Dimensional Continuity Equation:

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial (r^* u_r^*)}{\partial r^*} + \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial z^*} = 0}$$

2. Non-Dimensional Radial Momentum Equation:

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial t^*} + u_r^* \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{u_\theta^*}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial z^*} - \frac{(u_\theta^*)^2}{r^*} = -\frac{\partial P^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial (r^* u_r^*)}{\partial r^*} \right) + \frac{\partial^2 u_r^*}{(r^*)^2 \partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} - \frac{2}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} \right)}$$

3. Non-Dimensional Azimuthal Momentum Equation:

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial t^*} + u_r^* \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{u_\theta^*}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* \frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial z^*} + \frac{u_r^* u_\theta^*}{r^*} = -\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial P^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial (r^* u_\theta^*)}{\partial r^*} \right) + \frac{1}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^*}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{2}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} \right)}$$

4. Non-Dimensional Axial Momentum Equation:

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial t^*} + u_r^* \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{u_\theta^*}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial \theta} + u_z^* \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial z^*} = -\frac{\partial P^*}{\partial z^*} + \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial}{\partial r^*} \left(r^* \left(\frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial r^*} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{(r^*)^2} \frac{\partial^2 u_z^*}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} \right)}$$

It is evident that, in addition to all the kinematic transformations, the kinematic viscosity ν has been replaced by the Reynolds number in the non-dimensional equations.

6 Boundary Conditions for the Flow Field

Although the governing equations control the flow field parameters and their gradients, without the correct boundary conditions they cannot predict the flow field accurately. It is the boundary conditions that determine the abrupt changes, value shifts, and pattern formation within the flow field. The Navier-Stokes equations (or any PDEs in fluid mechanics) admit multiple possible solutions unless boundary conditions constrain them. Boundary conditions ensure a unique and physically realistic solution. The boundary conditions employed below are of Dirichlet type (prescribed values), Neumann type (prescribed gradients), and symmetry type; formal definitions of these and other boundary condition types can be found in standard references [8,9].

6.1 Boundary Conditions for Flow Through a Pipe

In this subsection, we discuss in detail the boundary conditions required at the pipe boundaries to obtain accurate flow field results.

Figure 6: The longitudinal view of the pipe flow describing the various boundary locations and the flow geometry.

1. **INLET:** The inlet is the boundary through which fluid enters the pipe, shown as the left boundary in the figure above. In general, there are two types of inlet boundary conditions: (i) a *pressure inlet*, where the entry pressure is prescribed, and (ii) a *velocity inlet*, where the mass flow rate and cross-sectional area are known, or equivalently, all three cylindrical velocity components (u_r , u_z , and u_θ) are specified. In the first case, the outlet pressure must also be known for the flow to be determined. The second case offers more flexibility at the outlet and is therefore preferred. Several common velocity inlet profiles are:

- **Constant Axial Flow:**

$$u_r = 0 \qquad u_\theta = 0 \qquad u_z = \text{Constant value (1,2,3...)}$$

In this case, the flow initially develops over several axial diameters into a Hagen-Poiseuille profile, with the maximum velocity reaching twice the inlet average velocity, after which the fully developed profile persists throughout the remaining axial length.

- **Parabolic Axial Flow:**

$$u_r = 0 \qquad u_\theta = 0 \qquad u_z = U_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{R^2} \right)$$

Here, a fully developed flow profile is imposed at the inlet, and the velocity distribution does not change significantly downstream. The inlet velocity varies parabolically with the radius, and the ratio of maximum to average velocity is $\frac{U_{\max}}{U_{\text{avg}}} = 2$.

- **Swirling Inlet Flow:**

$$u_r = 0 \qquad u_\theta = \omega r \qquad u_z = U_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{R^2} \right)$$

This type of flow exhibits significant variations in the axial, azimuthal, and radial velocity profiles, and may also exhibit the onset of flow instabilities at higher Reynolds numbers.

As evident from the above examples, it is essential to define the axial velocity at the inlet precisely, since only the axial velocity carries external mass into the system and drives the development of the flow field.

2. **WALLS OF THE PIPE:** Under the continuum hypothesis, the fluid is assumed to be relatively stationary with respect to the wall surface, i.e., it adheres to the wall (no-slip condition). The walls must be both no-slip and impermeable boundaries. Therefore:

$$(u_r)_{\text{fw}} = U_{r_{\text{walls}}} \qquad (u_\theta)_{\text{fw}} = U_{\theta_{\text{walls}}} \qquad (u_z)_{\text{fw}} = U_{z_{\text{walls}}}$$

If the wall is stationary, all velocity components vanish:

$$\implies (u_r)_{\text{fw}} = (u_\theta)_{\text{fw}} = (u_z)_{\text{fw}} = 0$$

In practice, no pressure boundary condition is imposed at the walls, since most modern solvers rely on pressure-velocity coupling algorithms; specifying both would over-constrain the solution and lead to convergence difficulties. If required, the Neumann condition states that the wall-normal pressure gradient must vanish: $\frac{\partial P}{\partial n} = 0$.

3. **OUTLET:** The outlet is the boundary through which the fluid exits the control volume. At the outlet, the shear stresses on the surface are set to zero (traction-free condition), while the normal stress equals the exit pressure. This requires a Dirichlet boundary condition for pressure at the outlet.

$$\tau_{zr} = \tau_{z\theta} = 0 \qquad \tau_{zz} = p_{\text{outlet}}$$

Note: This traction-based outlet condition (zero shear stress, prescribed normal stress) is one of several possible treatments. Alternative approaches used in CFD include pressure-outlet with zero-gradient velocity, convective outflow conditions, or buffer-zone methods. The choice depends on the physics of the problem and the numerical scheme employed.

For dimensional units:

$$\begin{aligned}\Rightarrow \tau_{zr} &= \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \right) = 0 \\ \Rightarrow \tau_{z\theta} &= \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial \theta} \right) = 0 \\ \Rightarrow \tau_{zz} &= 2\mu \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = p\end{aligned}$$

Setting the exit gauge pressure to $P_{\text{outlet}} = 0$ (appropriate when the outlet discharges to the atmosphere):

$$\begin{aligned}\Rightarrow \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\partial \tau_{z\theta}}{\partial z} &= \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z \partial \theta} \right) = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta}{\partial z^2} = 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\partial \tau_{zr}}{\partial z} &= \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z \partial r} \right) = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} = 0\end{aligned}$$

These are essential Outlet BCs for dimensional flows.

For non-dimensional units:

$$\begin{aligned}\Rightarrow \tau_{z^*r^*} &= \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial u_r^*}{\partial z^*} + \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial r^*} \right) = 0 \\ \Rightarrow \tau_{z^*\theta} &= \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial u_\theta^*}{\partial z^*} + \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial \theta} \right) = 0 \\ \Rightarrow \tau_{z^*z^*} &= \frac{2}{Re} \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial z^*} = p^*\end{aligned}$$

Setting the exit gauge pressure to $P_{\text{outlet}}^* = 0$ (appropriate when the outlet discharges to the atmosphere):

$$\begin{aligned}\Rightarrow \frac{\partial u_z^*}{\partial z^*} &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\partial \tau_{z^*\theta}}{\partial z^*} &= \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z^*}{\partial z^* \partial \theta} \right) = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial^2 u_\theta^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} = 0 \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\partial \tau_{z^*r^*}}{\partial z^*} &= \frac{1}{Re} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_r^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z^*}{\partial z^* \partial r^*} \right) = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial^2 u_r^*}{\partial (z^*)^2} = 0\end{aligned}$$

These are essential Outlet BCs for non-dimensional flows.

4. **AXIS OF SYMMETRY:** The axis of symmetry is a boundary about which the flow field is symmetric. Since no mass or energy crosses this boundary, the normal derivatives vanish. This is typically the z axis, with the radial direction being perpendicular to it. At $r = 0$, the following conditions apply:

Dirichlet conditions (required to ensure a finite, uniquely defined velocity field at the axis):

$$u_r|_{r=0} = 0 \quad u_\theta|_{r=0} = 0$$

The radial and azimuthal velocities must vanish at the axis; otherwise the velocity field would be multi-valued or singular at $r = 0$.

Neumann conditions (symmetry/smoothness):

$$\left. \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} \right|_{r=0} = 0 \quad \left. \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \right|_{r=0} = 0$$

The axial velocity and pressure must have zero radial gradient at the axis to ensure smooth, symmetric profiles.

These are the essential boundary conditions for fluid flow through a cylindrical pipe.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, the Navier-Stokes equations for an incompressible Newtonian fluid in cylindrical coordinates have been derived from first principles. Starting from the kinematic relations between Cartesian and cylindrical coordinate systems, we established the expressions for velocity and acceleration in curvilinear coordinates. A detailed force balance on an infinitesimal cylindrical element — accounting for pressure, viscous, and curvature forces — yielded the three momentum equations along the radial, azimuthal, and axial directions, along with the continuity equation.

The constitutive relations for a Newtonian fluid in cylindrical coordinates were derived independently, paying careful attention to the geometric effects that distinguish them from their Cartesian counterparts (notably the u_r/r and u_θ/r terms arising from the curvature of coordinate lines). Substituting these into the general momentum equations and simplifying using the continuity constraint produced the full dimensional Navier-Stokes equations.

Subsequently, these equations were non-dimensionalised using the pipe diameter D and average axial inlet velocity $U_{z_{\text{avg}}}$ as reference scales, revealing the Reynolds number $Re = DU_{z_{\text{avg}}}/\nu$ as the sole governing parameter for this class of incompressible flows. Finally, the essential boundary conditions at the inlet, walls, outlet, and axis of symmetry were discussed in both dimensional and non-dimensional forms.

These non-dimensional equations and boundary conditions form the complete mathematical framework required for analytical or numerical solution of viscous pipe flow problems in cylindrical geometry. By consolidating the entire derivation chain — from coordinate kinematics to final non-dimensional equations — in a single document with explicit intermediate steps, this work aims to serve as a self-contained reference for students and practitioners working with cylindrical flow formulations.

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